

OPTIMUM SOLUTION for EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT of UNIVERSITY

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Abstract— Universities of education today have complex administrative system, which have the responsibility of taking care of need of students, faculty, the administrators and general public. It is also required to manage with modern facilities with the common mission like acquisition, the transmission and the application of knowledge which is relevant to society. Proper understanding of the components of the system and their interrelationships leads to proper coordination in the system. The paper aims in developing Goal Programming model for the proper allocation of resources in the university in an efficient and effective manner. During allocation of the resources multiple goals are taken into account such as operating system and financial constraints of the University. Many goals are taken into consideration and while trying to achieve that goals we observe the deviations which helps the manager to take proper decision. Best decision always helps the organization to run effectively. Study helps in improvement of university in overall.

Keywords—Goal programming, deviation, underachievement, overachievement, Decision-making

I. INTRODUCTION

As universities around the world face funding cuts and an increasingly competitive recruitment environment, they are coming up with increasingly creative ways to attract students and boost their brand. Improvement of the University depends on many criteria's. To improve the University areas like staff salary, maintenance charges, service charges, cultural expenditure, sport expenditures, departmental technical activities, fees collection, development charges, funds/grants received, marketing investments, modernization of the buildings etc. of every department plays very important role. Head of the University must know where exactly plan deviates/failures to improve the institution.

II. METHODOLOGY

Our study involves the importance to these areas and each areas are taken as goals and goals are converted as equation. Using goal programming technique fixing the target and trying to identify the deviation of the goals. This helps the higher authority to take decision where exactly he wants to improve and he can concentrate in the area which he has to improve and can lead the university, qualitatively as well as quantitatively (with profit). University has different programs which involves various branches. Our study has taken 2 different programs (UG & PG) and each program has 6 branches and calculation has taken over two semesters

III. GOAL PROGRAMMING MODEL

Director of the University will consider the goals and fix the targets. Goal programming model is created based on the following goals

A. To Minimize the Maintenance Charges:

Maintenance charge is one of the important expenditure of the any university. To maintain university with profitable manner one should control the maintenance charges like electricity expenditure, water expenditure, departmental maintenance, expenditure for cleanliness etc

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 M_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq M_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 M_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_1^- - d_1^+ = M_T$$

- i represents different programs(UG and PG)
- j represents different branches(6 branches in both UG and PG)
- t represents two semesters of the year

B. To Maintain the Service Charges (Machines, instruments and computers servicing charges):

Machines in some of the departments and instruments as we use in laboratories and computers when we use years by years they require servicing and new software's in case of computers. Each department will have different service charges in different semesters. Taking this as another goal in the problem and the mathematical equation is

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 S_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq S_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 S_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_2^- - d_2^+ = S_T$$

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C. To Control the Cultural Expenditure:

Each program organizes cultural programs in both the semesters. Cultural programs may be branch wise or program wise. Expenditure can be considered and target of expenditure is fixed as C_T

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 C_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq C_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 C_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_3^- - d_3^+ = C_T$$

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D. Raising the Project Funds:

Different projects can be applied from various departments and some agencies like AICTE, KSC, VGST etc release the funds to finish the projects. Getting project funds are very essential for the University. It adds value to the institution or university.

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 F_{ijt} x_{ijt} \geq F_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 F_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_4^- - d_4^+ = F_T$$

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E. Maximizing Fees Collection: Fees collection depends on how many students admitted to each program and the fees fixed to the program. By maintaining the quality and vigorous marketing university admission can improve

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 FE_{ijt} x_{ijt} \geq FE_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 FE_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_5^- - d_5^+ = FE_T$$

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F. To control the sports expenditure:

Each program organizes sports competition in both the semesters. Sports competitions may be branch wise or program wise. Expenditure can be considered and target of expenditure is fixed as C_T

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 SP_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq SP_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 SP_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_6^- - d_6^+ = SP_T$$

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G. To Minimize the Development (Modernization) charges:

To increase the admission, modernization of the buildings upgrading the architecture is very important

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 D_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq D_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 D_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_7^- - d_7^+ = D_T$$

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H. To Minimize the Departmental Technical Activities Expenditure:

Every semester it is mandatory that technical activities need to happen in the departments to maintain the quality of the university. Students can upgrade their knowledge using this platform. Active participation of students and teachers helps to upgrade themselves. University has to spent good amount for giving the prizes and to call external industry people to share knowledge to the students in this platform

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 T_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq T_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{10} \sum_{j=1}^4 \sum_{t=1}^2 T_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_8^- - d_8^+ = T_T$$

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I. To Minimize the Examination Expenditures:

In every semester to organize examination some expenditures are involved. The study can take up controlling the expenditure as one of the goals and it can be denoted mathematically as follows

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 E_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq E_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 E_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_9^- - d_9^+ = E_T$$

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J. Controlling The Marketing Investment (branding and advertising expenditure): Branding and advertising of the University and each program is very important it involves separate expenditures. Marketing investment is also should not exceed the fixed percentage of the Annual income. Taking marketing as another important goal of the study and mathematical formulation is given by

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 B_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq B_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 B_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_{10}^- - d_{10}^+ = B_T$$

i represents different programs(UG and PG)

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K. To Control The Salary Expenditure: It is very important to maintain the quality of University and it requires highly qualified and well experienced faculty members. But the salary of the total faculty members should not exceed the 30% of the tuition fees

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 SL_{ijt} x_{ijt} \leq SL_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 SL_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_{11}^- - d_{11}^+ = SL_T$$

i represents different programs(UG and PG)

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L. To Maximize The Conversion Rate of Garbage in The Campus:

Wet garbage in the canteen can be converted into fuel & this reduces the cost of fuel required for cooking. This

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 G_{ijt} x_{ijt} \geq G_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 G_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_{12}^- - d_{12}^+ = G_T$$

i represents different programs(UG and PG)

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t represents two semesters of the year

M.To Maximize The Consultancy Services:

To maximize the consultancy services with the college lab facility from each program

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 C_{ijt} x_{ijt} \geq C_T$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^6 \sum_{t=1}^2 C_{ijt} x_{ijt} + d_{13}^- - d_{13}^+ = C_T$$

i represents different programs(UG and PG)

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IV.PRIORITIES FOR THE GOALS

Assign the priorities for Fees collection, Project fund, consultancy services, garbage conversion, Maintenance charges, service charges, cultural expenditure, Modernization of the campus, departmental

activities expenditure, Examination expenditure, Marketing expenditure, Salary expenditure, Sports expenditure Goals taken as $P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}, P_{11}, P_{12}, P_{13}$.

V.ACHIEVEMENT FUNCTION

$$P_1 d_5^- + P_2 d_4^- + P_3 d_{13}^- + P_4 d_{12}^+ + P_5 d_5^+ + P_6 d_6^+ + P_7 d_7^+ + P_8 d_7^+ + P_9 d_8^+ + P_{10} d_9^+ + P_{11} d_{10}^+ + P_{12} d_{11}^+ + P_{13} d_6^+$$

VI.RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

Implementation of the model can be done using the statistical values. Once the Statistical data is collected, we need to apply in the model in future study. Formulated general goal programming model with statistical values, may be solved using software's like Tora, mat lab, Lingo, excel solver etc. On solving we get the deviation values of the goals interims of overachievement and underachievement values. Values of underachievement and overachievement may help to take decision towards the improvement of the University. Deviation values helps in taking up the decisions in the unit. We solve the model by using software like Excel Solver, Tora, LINGO or MATLAB by using following steps

- Input the statistical values into the model.
- Set up the objective function and constraints as defined.
- Run the solver to find the optimal values which minimize the total deviation from the goals.

We Interpret Results by using deviational values. These indicate how much each goal deviates from its target, providing insights into areas of over performance and underperformance.

Decision Making and Improvement

- Decision Insights: Use deviational values to prioritize areas for improvement. Goals with significant underachievement can be targeted for immediate attention.
- Action Planning: Based on the results, formulate action plans to address weaknesses and enhance strengths of university identified by the model.
- Iterative Process: Continuously collect new data, update the model, and refine strategies to ensure ongoing improvement.

By implementing this approach, you can effectively use statistical data and goal programming to drive decision-making and improvement efforts within the university setting.

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